

Efficient Radio Resource Management for Rate Maximization in LEO Multi-satellite Systems

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Abstract—The communication satellite system exemplifies a typical case of resource limitations, given the scarcity and value of spectrum and satellite power. This scarcity is further compounded by the rapid progress of mega-constellations Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites. In this paper, we examine the resource allocation challenges in a dense LEO satellite constellation, where efficient management of spectrum, power, and beams is crucial for enhancing network capacity. A Radio Resource Management (RRM) technique that aims to maximize network throughput by judiciously distributing resources is proposed. Despite the NP-hard complexity of the problem, the proposed solution adopts a methodology that balances efficiency and computational complexity. We introduce an efficient algorithm to address the power and subcarrier allocation problem with predetermined beam assignments, which is then utilized for region-satellite allocation. Numerical results demonstrate the superior performance of our algorithm, achieving higher sum rates compared to alternative methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

The seamless integration of satellite communications into 6G networks is a crucial development, offering extensive coverage and affordable connectivity, especially in areas where building terrestrial infrastructure is impractical or too costly [1]. Of notable interest within this integration are LEO satellites due their low propagation latency, improved data transfer rates, and lower launch costs compared to GEO satellites.

Optimal resource allocation is crucial to augmenting network capacity in densely populated satellite constellations. Various resources, including spectrum, power, and beams, must be efficiently managed by satellites to fulfill predefined objectives. Nonetheless, this task is anything but straightforward, given the intricate interplay among resources and due to the satellite movement and the dynamic network topology. It is important to emphasize that, within the context of multi-beam LEO satellites, feasible power allocation is of paramount concern due to the limited power capacity of micro and small satellites. The primary goal of power allocation in satellite systems is to enhance system performance while adhering to the constraints imposed by limited power resources on the satellite. Efficient power utilization has the potential to enhance signal gain and improve Quality of Service (QoS) for users. For instance, [2] presents two-stage multi-objective approaches employing heuristic optimization algorithms, although the resultant solution tends to be computationally demanding. Authors in [3] focus on minimizing the number of active beams to achieve the desired capacity, without considering power consumption. Although [4] addresses the joint allocation of power and bandwidth, but research in this area still relatively limited. While reconfigurable beams offer enhanced flexibility, particularly advantageous for small satellites [5], they introduce additional challenges such as beam

width, shape, and orientation, further complicating resource management. Recently, authors in [6] investigated the the joint optimization problem of beam placement and transmit power to maximize the sum spectral efficiency in multibeam LEO systems.

While some literature focuses on jointly optimizing various radio resources, these studies predominantly address scenarios involving a single satellite [2]–[5]. The work in [6] considers single channel and one ground node per beam. In this paper, we investigate the optimization of radio resource management in multi-beam, multi-LEO satellite systems. Our focus lies on the judicious distribution of radio resources—such as beams, subchannels, and powers—among users, with the overarching aim of maximizing network throughput. Recognizing the NP-hard complexity inherent in this problem, we propose an efficient sub-optimal solution that adopts a two-step methodology, by addressing user-beam assignment and power-channel allocation in consecutive steps, thereby achieving a balance between efficiency and computational complexity.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the system model and formulates the problem. The proposed algorithm is described in Section III while the numerical results are provided in Section IV. Finally, section V draws the conclusions.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

As given in Figure 1, a constellation of multi-beam LEO satellites is considered. These LEO satellites provide coverage to several ground stations and user terminals on Earth. In the service area, the visible satellites are capable of emitting B beams, while individual user terminals are equipped with a single antenna. The set of LEO satellites that provide service to the target region is denoted as $\mathcal{L} = \{1, \dots, l, \dots, L\}$, and the set of user terminals is denoted as $\mathcal{U} = \{1, \dots, u, \dots, U\}$. The set of beams that are generated by a given satellite l is denoted as B_l , and the whole set that collects all beams is denoted as \mathcal{B} . A full-frequency reuse scheme is adopted. Additionally, orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OFDMA) is employed to divide the spectrum of each beam into K subchannels to serve user terminals associated with the same beam. Here, $\mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, k, \dots, K\}$ represents the set of subchannels allocated per frequency band for each beam. In formulating the problem, we have focused on a particular time slot, thus omitting the variable t that denotes the time slot. It's imperative to include this variable when addressing different time slots. The network topology is assumed to be quasi-static within each time slot.

Fig. 1: Considered LEO satellite network scenario

It is assumed that the service area is denoted by \mathcal{S} , and this service area is divided into several regions grouped in the set $\mathcal{A} = \{1, \dots, a, \dots, A\}$. Each of these regions is served exclusively by one satellite beam that is allocated to this region. The binary variable $g_{l,b}^a$ is used to indicate if the a -th region is allocated to the b -th beam of the l -th satellite, i.e.,

$$g_{l,b}^a = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if region } a \text{ is allocated to } b \text{ beam of the satellite } l \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The binary variable C_k^u controls the spectrum allocation and is defined as follows:

$$C_k^u = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if subchannel } k \text{ is allocated to } u \text{ user terminal} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The assignment of the user terminal to a given beam is indicated by the binary variable n_b^u and defined as follows:

$$n_b^u = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if user terminal } u \text{ is served by beam } b \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) $\gamma_{l,b,k}^u$ of a user terminal u served by satellite l and beam b over a subchannel k is given by:

$$\gamma_{l,b,k}^u = \frac{P_{l,b,k} |h_{l,b,k}^u|^2}{\sigma_u^2 + I_o}, \quad (4)$$

where $P_{l,b,k}$ is the power allocated by the satellite l on the beam b and the subchannel k , and $h_{l,b,k}^u$ is the channel coefficient between the user terminal u and the satellite l over the subchannel k , which models large-scale and shadowed-Rician small-scale fadings. σ_u^2 represents the noise power, and I_o denotes the inter-beam interference.

Hence, the data rate of the subchannel k that is assigned to a user terminal u that is located in region a and served by satellite l and beam b is given by:

$$R_{l,b,k}^u = \Delta f \log_2 (1 + \gamma_{l,b,k}^u), \quad (5)$$

where Δf is the bandwidth of the subchannel k .

Accordingly, the data rate of a given user terminal u can be expressed as:

$$R_{l,b}^u = \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}_l} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} g_{l,b}^a \cdot C_k^u \cdot R_{l,b,k}^u \quad (6)$$

The objective of the resource management is to maximize the service area capacity by jointly pairing regions with beams and satellites, i.e., finding $\mathbf{G} = \{g_{l,b}^a, l \in \mathcal{L}, b \in \mathcal{B}, a \in$

$\mathcal{A}\}$, and find the subchannel assignment, i.e., $\mathbf{C} = \{C_k^u, k \in \mathcal{K}, u \in \mathcal{U}\}$ that maximizes (6). This work also investigates how to distribute the power budget, which is tantamount to designing the matrix that gathers all the power coefficients, i.e., $\mathbf{P} = \{P_{l,b,k}, l \in \mathcal{L}, b \in \mathcal{B}, k \in \mathcal{K}\}$. The optimization problem at a given time slot can be posed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{OP1: } & \max_{\mathbf{G}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{P}} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} R_{l,b}^u \\ \text{s.t. } & \text{(C1-OP1): } \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} g_{l,b}^a \leq 1, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, \\ & \text{(C2-OP1): } \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} g_{l,b}^a \leq 1, \quad \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, \\ & \text{(C3-OP1): } \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} n_b^u C_k^u \leq K, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, \\ & \text{(C4-OP1): } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} P_{l,b,k} \leq P_{\max}, \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall b \in \mathcal{B}_l, \\ & \text{(C5-OP1): } \mathbf{P} \geq 0, \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \\ & \text{(C6-OP1): } g_{l,b}^a \in \{1, 0\}, \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, \\ & \text{(C7-OP1): } C_k^u \in \{1, 0\}, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \end{aligned}$$

where P_{\max} denotes the maximum transmission power per beam. C1-OP1 guarantees that each beam can be allocated to only one region, while C2-OP1 guarantees that each region is allocated to only one beam to reduce inter-beam interference. C3-OP1 limits the number of available subchannels per beam to K . C4-OP1 ensures that the power constraint on each beam is satisfied. C5-OP1 guarantees positive power values. Finally, C6-OP1 and C7-OP1 refer to the fact that \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{C} are binary variables.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The optimization problem OP1 is an NP-hard problem, adding complexity to finding the optimal solution. Considering that OP1 should be solved at each time slot due to the mobility of LEO satellites, dealing with its computational challenges is crucial. Consequently, this section proposes an efficient two-step suboptimal approach to tackle OP1.

To commence, let's assume that a given region $a \in \mathcal{A}$ is illuminated by a specific beam $b \in \mathcal{B}_l$. As a result, the binary variables $g_{l,b}^a$ and n_b^u are predetermined, simplifying the problem OP1 to a different problem. Upon defining the beam assignment, this new problem involves the distribution of available power and subchannels among user terminals within that beam. Mathematically, this can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{OP2: } & \max_{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{P}} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b} R_{l,b}^u \\ \text{s.t. } & \text{(C1-OP2): } \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} n_b^u C_k^u \leq K, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, \\ & \text{(C2-OP2): } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} P_{l,b,k} \leq P_{\max}, \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall b \in \mathcal{B}_l, \\ & \text{(C3-OP2): } \mathbf{P} \geq 0, \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \\ & \text{(C4-OP2): } C_k^u \in \{1, 0\}, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}_b, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \end{aligned}$$

where U_b are the user terminals inside the beam b .

The optimization problem OP2 presents a challenging combinatorial optimization task, notorious for its exponential complexity concerning input size. Nonetheless, despite this complexity, an optimal solution can be obtained through a two-step approach. The inter-beam interference is assumed to be approximately non-significant (based on considering that edge UEs should have different subchannels as detailed later when dealing with the allocation of the variable n_b^u). Accordingly, one can perform the allocation of subchannels to user terminals initially, followed by the optimization of power allocation in the second step. Interestingly, viewing OP2 as a single-user optimization problem in the second step facilitates its resolution. Upon closer examination, OP2 bears resemblance to the downlink radio resource allocation quandary encountered in terrestrial networks. Drawing an analogy to terrestrial downlink optimization and as proven in [7], the maximum sum rate can be obtained by assigning the subchannel to the user terminal with the best channel in the first step. Once the subchannels are allocated, i.e., \mathbf{C} is determined, the optimization problem OP2 can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{OP3: } & \max_{\mathbf{P}} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} R_{l,b}^u \\ \text{s.t. (C1-OP3): } & \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} P_{l,b,k} \leq P_{\max}, \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall b \in B_l, \\ & \text{(C2-OP3): } \mathbf{P} \geq 0, \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \end{aligned}$$

The problem OP3 is a convex optimization problem that can be solved by the convex optimization framework. Algorithm 1 summarizes the procedures to that needed to be followed to solve OP2.

The variable n_b^u is determined based on the receiving power from the different beams by a given UE. Hence, if unit power is transmitted by the satellite over all beams, the UE is allocated to the region/beam where the maximum power is received. If the UE is receiving high power from two or more beams, it is still allocated to the region/beam of the maximum received power, but it's considered as edge UE. Once Algorithm 1 is performed, the result of Algorithm 1 is analyzed to check that edge UEs have different subchannels. In the case of having two edge UEs with the same subchannel and giving that the target is to maximize the capacity, the UE with the lower SNR is removed and the subchannel is allocated to the UE with the next maximum value. Different criteria should be followed with the edge user in case of having fairness or service priority constraints.

Successfully addressing the problem when a specific region is assigned to a designated beam and satellite, as encountered in OP2, relies heavily on our capability to shift focus from moving from OP1 to addressing OP2. This shift underscores the need for developing an efficient methodology to make these assignments. To initiate this process, we begin by constructing the matrix \mathbb{D} with size $A \times L$, where each element $(a, l) \in D$ represents the data rate achieved by solving OP2

Algorithm 1 Subchannel and Power Allocation

Input:

- \mathcal{A} : Set of regions.
 - B_l : Set of beams for each satellite.
 - U_b : Set of user terminals within each beam.
 - $g_{l,b}^a$: Binary variables representing illumination of region a by beam b .
 - n_b^u : Binary variables representing user terminal u to a given beam b .
 - P_{\max} : Maximum power that can be transmitted by each satellite on a given beam.
 - \mathcal{K} : Set of subchannels.
-

Output:

- $P_{l,b,k}$ and C_k^u which maximize the sum rate of beam b
-

STEPS

- 1: Set $C_k^u = 0, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$ and $\forall u \in U_b$.
 - 2: **for** $k = 1$ to K **do**
 $u^* = \arg \max_u \{h_{l,k}^u\};$
 $C_k^{(u^*)} = 1.$
 - 3: **end for**
 Use C_k^u to solve OP3.
Return $P_{l,b,k}$ and C_k^u .
-

when the region a is illuminated by a beam of the satellite l . Hence, the matrix \mathbb{D} can be written mathematically as:

$$\mathbb{D} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{OP2}_{|(a=1,l=1)} & \cdots & \text{OP2}_{|(a=1,l=L)} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \text{OP2}_{|(a=A,l=1)} & \cdots & \text{OP2}_{|(a=A,l=L)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Once the matrix \mathbb{D} is constructed, the region-satellite assignment process is started by scanning matrix \mathbb{D} row-wise. Each region is then assigned to the satellite that yields the maximum data rate. Formally, for a given row $a \in A$, we compute $l^* = \arg \max_{l \in \mathcal{L}} \text{OP2}_{|_{a,l}}$ and store the outcome of solving $\text{OP2}_{|_{a,l^*}}$ as the power and subchannel assignment. Upon completing the assignment for a given region (i.e., given row of \mathbb{D}), we check whether satellite l^* has allocated all its beams. If so, we update the matrix \mathbb{D} by removing the column corresponding to the satellite l^* . The steps are repeated until all regions or beams are allocated. These steps are summarized in Algorithm 2 below. The computational complexity of the proposed algorithm is $\mathcal{O}(ALK \log K)$.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In order to replicate the configuration of an actual satellite constellation, MATLAB is utilized to simulate Walker star satellites. The constellation's parameters primarily draw inspiration from STARLINK satellites, which are detailed in Table I alongside other key simulation parameters.

In the simulation, the satellite constellation comprises 72 orbits positioned at an altitude of 550 kilometers. Each orbit

Algorithm 2 Region-Satellite Assignment

Input:

- \mathcal{A} : Set of regions.
 - \mathcal{L} : Set of satellite beams.
-

Output:

Assignment of each region to a satellite beam, along with corresponding power and subchannel allocation, i.e., G, C, P .

STEPS

- 1: Construct matrix \mathbb{D} with dimensions $A \times L$. Use Algorithm 1 to obtain the entries of matrix \mathbb{D} .
 - 2: **while** there are unassigned regions or unallocated satellite beams **do**
 - 3: **for** each unassigned region a in A **do**
 Find the satellite beam l^* that maximizes the data rate for region a : $l^* = \arg \max_{l \in \mathcal{L}} \text{OP2}_{|a,l}$.
 Assign region a to satellite beam l^* and store power and subchannel allocation result of $\text{OP2}_{(a,l^*)}$.
 - 4: **if** all beams of satellite l^* are assigned **then**
 Remove column l^* from matrix \mathbb{D} .
 - 5: **end if**
 - 6: **end for**
 - 7: **end while**
 Return the assignment of each region to a satellite beam, along with corresponding power and subchannel allocation.
-

Fig. 2: Simulation topology with two satellites and 32 beam centers. The considered service area is the rectangle formed by the beam centers and the black circles indicate the satellites coverage area.

accommodates 20 satellites, characterized by a fixed inclination of 45 degrees. The focus of coverage lies specifically over Spain. For the sake of simplicity and without sacrificing accuracy, the evaluation considers a specific time-slot when two satellites pass over Spain, identified by their Earth-Centered, Earth-Fixed (ECEF) positions: $1.0 \times 10^6 \times (5.3824, -0.1280, 4.3604)$ and $1.0 \times 10^6 \times (5.3448, -0.4080, 4.3893)$. Illustrating an example with 32 beam centers, Figure 2 showcases the distribution of satellites, the service area, and the locations of the beam centers.

TABLE I: Main simulation parameters

Parameter	Value
Satellites altitude	550 Km
Orbit inclination	45°
Number of orbits	72
Earth beam centers possible values	[16 32 56 100 182]
Beams per satellite	Half of earth beam centers
No. Users	500
No. of satellites over the service area	2
Transmitting antenna gain	30.5 dBi
Beam half power beamwidth	4.4127
Diameter of the satellite antenna	0.2 m
Receiving antenna gain	39.7 dBi
Carrier frequency	20 GHz (Ka band)
No. Subchannels	20
Maximal Satellite power	1200 W
Maximal beam power	Maximal Satellite power / Beams per satellite
Minimum elevation angle	40°
Noise floor	-122.20 dBW
Beam bandwidth	200 MHz

For comparison reasons, the following algorithms are defined:

- **Proposed:** This algorithm is outlined in Section III.
- **Scheme 1:** This algorithm involves randomly allocating beam centers to satellites, as well as random channel allocation and user selection. The final power allocation is optimized to maximize the rate.
- **Scheme 2:** Similar to scheme 1, this algorithm also employs random beam center allocation to satellites and random channel allocation. However, the power is uniformly allocated across the subchannels.
- **Scheme 3:** This algorithm randomly allocates subchannels to users but performs beam center to satellite allocation and power allocation based on the proposed algorithm.
- **Scheme 4:** This algorithm mirrors the proposed approach, except for the beam center to satellite allocation, which is performed randomly.

Figure 3 illustrates the achieved sum rate in Kbit/Hz/s plotted against the number of user terminals for different algorithms employing 32 beam centers. It is evident that the proposed algorithm outperforms the other algorithms. As the number of user terminals increases, the sum rate also increases due to the algorithm's increased options for allocation. However, Schemes 1, 2, and 3 exhibit saturation in sum rate at a certain number of user terminals, as their random nature does not benefit from additional allocation options and the scheme does not prevent interference between beams. In this simulated example, subchannel allocation has a more pronounced effect on performance than beam center allocation, given the consideration of only two satellites. This justifies the close performance of Scheme 4 to the proposed algorithm and the lower performance of Schemes 1, 2, and 3. While the difference may seem minor between the proposed and Scheme 4 in Figure 3, it's important to note that Scheme 4 mirrors part of the proposed algorithm and the significance of

Fig. 3: Sum rate vs. number of user terminals with 32 beam centers.

this distinction becomes apparent when considering that the curves represent data rates in Kbit/S/Hz . As the number of satellites increases, it is expected that the gap between Scheme 4 and the proposed algorithm will widen. Due to the higher transmission power resulting in higher SNR values across different subchannels, the performance of the optimized power and uniform allocation methods remains close. However, this gap is anticipated to increase in scenarios with lower SNR values.

Similar observations can be concluded from Figure 4, where the sum rate of the different algorithms is evaluated vs. number of beam centers. It is also evident that the disparity between the proposed algorithm and Scheme 4 widens in Figure 4 as the number of subchannels increase. This widening gap can be attributed to the increased availability of resources within the system, which significantly impacts the performance of random-based allocation methods.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a dense LEO satellite constellation is considered where efficient resource allocation plays a pivotal role in enhancing network capacity. Managing spectrum, power, and beams effectively is imperative for satellites to achieve predefined objectives. However, this task is complex due to dynamic network topology and satellite movement. RRM technique to deal with the RRM challenge in LEO satellites which aims at maximizing network throughput through judicious resource distribution is proposed. Despite the NP-hard complexity, the proposed sub-optimal solution adopts a two-step methodology, balancing efficiency, and computational complexity. Results reveal the superior performance of the proposed algorithm in achieving higher sum rates compared to others. The proposed algorithm achieves increasing sum rate while increasing user terminals and satellite subchannels which emphasizes the efficacy of the proposed approach in diverse satellite communication scenarios. We are progressing

Fig. 4: Sum rate vs. number of subchannels with 32 beam centers.

towards expanding this work to include fairness in average user throughput over time. Additionally, we are working on incorporating an artificial intelligence-based scheme to enhance system performance even further.

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